

A NOTE ON PARTIALLY-GREEDY BASES IN QUASI-BANACH SPACES

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ABSTRACT. We continue with the study of greedy-type bases in quasi-Banach spaces started in [3]. In this paper, we study partially-greedy bases focusing our attention in two main results:

- Characterization of partially-greedy bases in quasi-Banach spaces in terms of quasi-greediness and different conservative-like properties.
- Given a C -partially-greedy basis in a quasi-Banach space, there exists a “renorming” such that the basis is 1-partially-greedy.

1. INTRODUCTION

For several years, how to represent a function f in a particular space \mathbb{X} , has been considered a quite important problem in the area of Mathematical Analysis, that is, given $f \in \mathbb{X}$, we want to obtain

$$f = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \mathbf{e}_n,$$

for a given basic functions $(\mathbf{e}_n)_{n=1}^{\infty}$ and for a suitable scalars a_n (coefficients). In literature we can find different examples of such representations as for instance Fourier series of functions or Taylor expansions. In Functional Analysis, one consider expansions with regard to a basis, that is, we could consider that $\mathcal{B} = (\mathbf{e}_n)_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is a Schauder or a Markushevich basis.

One of the main goals of Approximation Theory is to find good approximations of f in terms of finite sums. Concretely, we want to find algorithms of approximation $(T_m)_{m=1}^{\infty}$, where

$$T_m(f) = \sum_{n \in A} b_n \mathbf{e}_n,$$

A is a finite set of cardinality m and b_n could be different from the original coefficients of f . Moreover, we would like to have that $(T_m)_{m=1}^{\infty}$ produces a “good approximation” (that could be interpreted taking into account our preferences).

Since 1999, in the field of Non-Linear Approximation, one of the most important algorithms that several researchers have studied is the Greedy Algorithm $(G_m)_{m=1}^{\infty}$, where for an element f in \mathbb{X} , the algorithm selects the biggest coefficients of f in modulus. This algorithm was introduced by S. V. Konyagin and V. N. Temlyakov in [13] and different and new properties about greedy approximation have been analyzed by different authors, among them S. J. Dilworth, N. J. Kalton, D. Kutzarova, P. Wojtaszczyk, etc (see [10, 11, 15]). In this paper,

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we focus our attention in the following property that was introduced in [11]: there exists a positive constant C such that

$$\|f - G_m(f)\| \leq C\|f - S_m(f)\|, \quad \forall f \in \mathbb{X}, \forall m \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (1.1)$$

where S_m denotes the m th partial sum. The importance of this property resides in the fact that we want to compare if the non-linear approximation is better than linear approximation. Here, we extend the main known results about (1.1) in Banach spaces for the case of quasi-Banach spaces, using recent results proved in [3].

The structure of the paper is the following: in Section 2 we give the basic definitions about bases in quasi-Banach spaces and some operators. In Section 3 we give the definition of the Greedy Algorithm, we talk about some greedy-type bases and we analyze some properties about conservativeness. In Section 4 we give the main characterization of partially-greedy bases in quasi-Banach spaces and, finally, in Section 5, we talk about renorming of quasi-Banach spaces using greedy-type bases.

2. PRELIMINARIES ON QUASI-BANACH SPACES

We say that the map $\|\cdot\| : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ defined on a vector space \mathbb{X} over $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{R}$ or \mathbb{C} is a **quasi-norm** if

- a) $\|f\| > 0$ for all $f \neq 0$,
- b) $\|tf\| = |t|\|f\|$, for all $t \in \mathbb{F}$ and $f \in \mathbb{X}$,
- c) there exists a positive constant k such that for all $f, g \in \mathbb{X}$,

$$\|f + g\| \leq k(\|f\| + \|g\|).$$

Given $p \in (0, 1]$, a **p -norm** is a map $\|\cdot\| : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ satisfying a), b) and

- d) $\|f + g\|^p \leq \|f\|^p + \|g\|^p$, for all $f, g \in \mathbb{X}$.

Of course, d) implies c) with constant $k = 2^{1/p-1}$. If $\|\cdot\|$ is a quasi-norm (resp. p -norm) on \mathbb{X} such that defines a complete metrizable topology, then \mathbb{X} is called **quasi-Banach space** (resp. **p -Banach space**). Thanks to the Aoki-Rolewicz's Theorem (see [6],[14]), any quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} is p -convex, that is,

$$\left\| \sum_{i=1}^n x_j \right\| \leq C \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \|x_j\|^p \right)^{1/p}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, x_j \in \mathbb{X}.$$

This way, \mathbb{X} becomes p -Banach under a suitable renorming, for some $0 < p \leq 1$.

2.1. Bases. Throughout this paper, a **basis** in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} is a *semi-normalized and total Markushevich basis*, i.e., $\mathcal{B} = (\mathbf{e}_n)_{n=1}^\infty \subset \mathbb{X}$ verifies the following conditions:

- i) $[\mathbf{e}_n : n \in \mathbb{N}] = \mathbb{X}$, (completion)
- ii) there exists a unique sequence $(\mathbf{e}_n^*)_{n=1}^\infty \subset \mathbb{X}^*$, called **biorthogonal functionals**, such that $\mathbf{e}_n^*(\mathbf{e}_m) = \delta_{n,m}$,
- iii) if $\mathbf{e}_n^*(f) = 0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then $f = 0$, (totality)
- iv) there exist $c_1, c_2 > 0$ such that $0 < c_1 \leq \{\|\mathbf{e}_n\|, \|\mathbf{e}_n^*\|\} \leq c_2 < \infty$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. (semi-normalization).

Thanks to [3, Lemma 1.8], we now that if $f \in \mathbb{X}$, $f = \sum_{n=1}^\infty \mathbf{e}_n^*(f)\mathbf{e}_n$, where $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \mathbf{e}_n^*(f) = 0$ and the expansion is only formal but the assignment of coefficients is still unique. Also, we denote by $\text{supp}(f) = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : \mathbf{e}_n^*(f) \neq 0\}$.

Associated with a basis, we can consider the **projection operator** P_A , where for a finite set $A \subset \mathbb{N}$,

$$P_A(f) = \sum_{n \in A} \mathbf{e}_n^*(f) \mathbf{e}_n.$$

It is well known that if P_A is uniformly bounded, then \mathcal{B} is called unconditional. We write $S_k := P_{\{1, \dots, k\}}$ as the m th **partial sum**. Also, if there is a positive constant C such that

$$\|S_k(f)\| \leq C\|f\|, \quad \forall f \in \mathbb{X}, \forall k \in \mathbb{N},$$

we say that \mathcal{B} is a **Schauder basis**. Finally, if A is a finite set, we denote by Ψ_A the collection of signs ε :

$$\Psi_A := \{\varepsilon = (\varepsilon_n)_{n \in A} : |\varepsilon_n| = 1, n \in A\},$$

and $\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}] := \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}$ is the indicator sum:

$$\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A} = \sum_{n \in A} \varepsilon_n \mathbf{e}_n,$$

where $\varepsilon \in \Psi_A$. If $\varepsilon \equiv 1$, we write $\mathbf{1}_A$. As usual, if $A, B \subset \mathbb{N}$ are finite sets, we denote by $A < B$ if $\max A < \min B$.

2.2. p -convexity. Consider, for $0 < p \leq 1$, the following geometrical constants as in [3]:

$$\mathbf{A}_p = \frac{1}{(2^p - 1)^{1/p}},$$

and

$$\mathbf{B}_p = \begin{cases} 2^{1/p} \mathbf{A}_p & \text{if } \mathbb{F} = \mathbb{R}, \\ 4^{1/p} \mathbf{A}_p & \text{if } \mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}. \end{cases}$$

The following result is a collection of two corollaries of [3, Theorem 1.2], where this theorem plays the role of a substitute of the Bochner integral in the case of p -Banach spaces, for $0 < p \leq 1$.

Proposition 2.1 ([3, Corollaries 1.3 and 1.4]). *Let $\mathcal{B} = (\mathbf{e}_n)_{n=1}^\infty$ a basis in a p -Banach space and J a finite set. Then,*

a) *For any scalars $(a_n)_{n \in J}$ with $0 \leq a_n \leq 1$ and any $g \in \mathbb{X}$, we have*

$$\left\| g + \sum_{n \in J} a_n \mathbf{e}_n \right\| \leq \mathbf{A}_p \sup \left\{ \left\| g + \sum_{n \in A} \mathbf{e}_n \right\| : A \subseteq J \right\}.$$

b) *For any scalars $(a_n)_{n \in J}$ with $|a_n| \leq 1$ and any $g \in \mathbb{X}$, we have*

$$\left\| g + \sum_{n \in J} a_n \mathbf{e}_n \right\| \leq \mathbf{A}_p \sup \left\{ \left\| g + \sum_{n \in J} \varepsilon_n \mathbf{e}_n \right\| : |\varepsilon_n| = 1 \right\}.$$

c) *For any scalars $(a_n)_{n \in J}$ with $|a_n| \leq 1$, we have*

$$\left\| \sum_{n \in J} a_n \mathbf{e}_n \right\| \leq \mathbf{B}_p \sup_{A \subseteq J} \left\| \sum_{n \in A} \mathbf{e}_n \right\|.$$

3. THE GREEDY ALGORITHM AND GREEDY-TYPE BASES

For each $f \in \mathbb{X}$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}$, S. V. Konyagin and V. N. Temlyakov defined in [13] a **greedy sum** of f of order m by

$$G_m(f) = \sum_{n=1}^m e_{\pi(n)}^*(f) e_{\pi(n)},$$

where π is a **greedy ordering**, that is, $\pi : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a permutation such that $\text{supp}(f) \subseteq \pi(\mathbb{N})$ and $|e_{\pi(i)}^*(f)| \geq |e_{\pi(j)}^*(f)|$ for $i \leq j$. The series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e_{\pi(n)}^*(f) e_{\pi(n)}$ is called the **greedy series**. Also, $G_m(f) = P_A(f)$, where the set $A = \text{supp}(G_m(f))$ is called a **greedy set** and satisfies that $|A| = m$ and

$$\min_{n \in A} |e_n^*(f)| \geq \max_{n \notin A} |e_n^*(f)|.$$

3.1. Quasi-greedy and partially-greedy bases. To study the convergence of the greedy algorithm, we consider the following bases introduced by S. V. Konyagin and V. N. Temlyakov.

Definition 3.1 ([13]). *We say that a basis \mathcal{B} in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} is **quasi-greedy** if there is a positive constant C such that for all $f \in \mathbb{X}$,*

$$\|P_A(f)\| \leq C\|f\|, \quad (3.1)$$

whenever A is a finite greedy set of f . The smallest constant verifying (3.1) is called the **quasi-greedy constant** of the basis, it is denoted by $C_{qg} = C_{qg}[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}]$ and we say that \mathcal{B} is C_{qg} -quasi-greedy.

The following result was proved in [15] and [3]:

Theorem 3.2. *Let \mathcal{B} a basis in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} . The following are equivalent:*

- \mathcal{B} is quasi-greedy.
- For every $f \in \mathbb{X}$, the greedy series of $f \in \mathbb{X}$ converges.

Consider the following weaker version of quasi-greediness that we need for our purposes.

Definition 3.3 ([3]). *We say that a basis \mathcal{B} in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} is **quasi-greedy for largest coefficients** if there exists a positive constant C such that*

$$\|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\| \leq C\|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|, \quad (3.2)$$

for any finite set $A \subset \mathbb{N}$, any $\varepsilon \in \Psi_A$ and any $f \in \mathbb{X}$ such that $\text{supp}(f) \cap A = \emptyset$ and $\max_{n \in \text{supp}(f)} |e_n^*(f)| \leq 1$. The smallest constant verifying (3.2) is denoted by $C_{ql} = C_{ql}[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}]$ and we say that \mathcal{B} is C_{ql} -quasi-greedy for largest coefficients. Of course, $C_{ql} \leq C_{qg}$.

Since 1999, different types of convergence of the greedy algorithm have been studied by different authors introducing different greedy-type bases such as greedy bases and almost-greedy bases. These bases were introduced and characterized (in the context of Banach spaces) in [11, 13]. Recently, in [3], the authors characterized the same bases in the context of quasi-Banach spaces analyzing the lack of convexity in the results. Now, we study the characterization of partially-greedy bases.

Definition 3.4. *We say that a basis \mathcal{B} in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} is **partially-greedy** if there is a positive constant C such that, for all $f \in \mathbb{X}$ and all finite greedy set A of f ,*

$$\|f - P_A(f)\| \leq C \inf_{k \leq |A|} \|f - S_k(f)\|. \quad (3.3)$$

The smallest constant verifying (3.3) is called the **partially-greedy constant** of the basis, it is denoted by $C_{pg} = C_{pg}[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}]$ and we say that \mathcal{B} is C_{pg} -partially-greedy.

Remark 3.5. In [11], the authors defined partially-greedy as those bases where there exists a positive constant C such that

$$\|f - P_A(f)\| \leq C\|f - S_m(f)\|, \quad \forall f \in \mathbb{X}, \forall \text{ greedy set } |A| = m.$$

In the case when \mathcal{B} is a Schauder basis, both definitions are equivalent. We work with (3.3) inspired by the results obtained recently in [8].

In the following subsections, we give and analyze the main tools that we need for the characterization of partially-greediness in the context of quasi-Banach spaces.

3.2. The truncation operator. The following definitions follow from the truncation operator introduced in [10]. Take $f \in \mathbb{X}$, $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ finite and $\varepsilon \equiv \{\text{sign}(\mathbf{e}_n^*(f))\}$. Define, for $f \in \mathbb{X}$ and A a finite greedy set of f ,

$$\mathcal{U}(f, A) = \min_{n \in A} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A},$$

$$\mathcal{T}(f, A) = \mathcal{U}(f, A) + P_{A^c}(f).$$

These operators are called restricted truncation operator and truncation operator, respectively. Write the following quantities:

$$\Gamma_u = \Gamma_u[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}] = \sup\{\|\mathcal{U}(f, A)\| : \|f\| \leq 1, A \text{ greedy set of } f\},$$

$$\Gamma_t = \Gamma_t[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}] = \sup\{\|\mathcal{T}(f, A)\| : \|f\| \leq 1, A \text{ greedy set of } f\}.$$

Theorem 3.6 ([3, Theorem 3.13, Proposition 3.14]). *Let \mathcal{B} a quasi-greedy basis in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} . Then,*

- *The restricted truncation operator \mathcal{U} is uniformly bounded, that is, $\Gamma_u < \infty$. Also, if \mathbb{X} is a p -Banach space we have that $\Gamma_u \leq C_{qg}^2 \eta_p(C_{qg})$, where, for $u > 0$,*

$$\eta_p(u) = \min_{0 < t < 1} (1 - t^p)^{-1/p} (1 - (1 + \mathbf{A}_p^{-1} u^{-1} t)^{-p})^{-1/p},$$

and $\eta_p(C_{qg}) \lesssim C_{qg}^{1+1/p}$.

- *The truncation operator \mathcal{T} is uniformly bounded, that is, $\Gamma_t < \infty$. Also, if \mathbb{X} is a p -Banach space, we have that $\Gamma_t \leq C_{qg} (1 + C_{qg}^p \eta_p^p(C_{qg}))^{1/p}$.*

Remark 3.7. The estimate $\eta(C_{qg}) \lesssim C_{qg}^{1+1/p}$ was given in [3, Remark 3.9].

3.3. Properties about conservativeness. Consider the following property introduced recently in [8].

Definition 3.8 ([8]). *We say that a basis \mathcal{B} in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} is **partially-symmetric for largest coefficients** if there exists a positive constant C such that*

$$\|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\| \leq C\|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|, \quad (3.4)$$

for any pair of sets A, B , any $\varepsilon \in \Psi_A, \varepsilon' \in \Psi_B$ and any $f \in \mathbb{X}$ such that $|A| \leq |B|$, $\max_{n \in \text{supp}(f)} |\mathbf{e}_n^(f)| \leq 1$, $A < \text{supp}(f) \cup B$ and $B \cap \text{supp}(f) = \emptyset$. The smallest constant verifying (3.4) is denoted by $\Delta_{pl} = \Delta_{pl}[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}]$ and we say that \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients.*

Definition 3.9 ([11]). *We say that a basis \mathcal{B} in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} is **super-conservative** if there exists a positive constant C such that*

$$\|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\| \leq C\|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|, \quad (3.5)$$

for any pair of sets A, B with $|A| \leq |B|$ and $A < B$, and any choice of signs $\varepsilon \in \Psi_A, \varepsilon' \in \Psi_B$. The smallest constant verifying (3.5) is denoted by $\Delta_s = \Delta_s[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}]$ and we say that \mathcal{B} is Δ_s -super-conservative.

Also, we say that \mathcal{B} is **conservative** if (3.5) is satisfied with $\varepsilon \equiv \varepsilon' \equiv 1$, that is,

$$\|\mathbf{1}_A\| \leq C\|\mathbf{1}_B\|, \quad (3.6)$$

for any pair of sets A, B with $|A| \leq |B|$ and $A < B$. The smallest constant verifying (3.6) is denoted by $\Delta = \Delta[\mathcal{B}, \mathbb{X}]$ and we say that \mathcal{B} is Δ -**conservative**.

Of course, $\Delta \leq \Delta_s$. In the following result, we characterize when \mathcal{B} is partially-symmetric for largest coefficients.

Proposition 3.10. *Let \mathcal{B} a basis in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} .*

- a) \mathcal{B} is partially-symmetric for largest coefficients if and only if there exists a positive constant \mathbf{C} such that

$$\|f\| \leq \mathbf{C}\|f - S_k(f) + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon B}\|, \quad (3.7)$$

for any finite set B , any sign $\varepsilon \in \Psi_B$, any element $f \in \mathbb{X}$ and any natural number k such that $B \cap \text{supp}(f) = \emptyset$, $k < \min B$ and $\max_{n \in \text{supp}(f)} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \leq 1$. Moreover, if \mathbb{X} is a p -Banach space and \mathbf{C} is the smallest constant verifying (3.7), $\Delta_{pl} \leq \mathbf{C} \leq \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl}$.

- b) \mathcal{B} is partially-symmetric for largest coefficients if and only if \mathcal{B} is super-conservative and quasi-greedy for largest coefficients. Moreover, if \mathbb{X} is a p -Banach space,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_s &\leq \Delta_{pl}, \\ C_{ql} &\leq (1 + \Delta_{pl}^p)^{1/p}, \\ \Delta_{pl} &\leq (1 + (1 + \Delta_s^p)C_{ql}^p)^{1/p}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. First of all, we prove a). Assume (3.7) and to show that \mathcal{B} is partially-symmetric for largest coefficients, take A, B, f, ε and ε' as in 3.4. Define $f' := f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}$ and take $k := \max A$. Thus,

$$S_k(f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}) = \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}. \quad (3.8)$$

Hence, applying (3.7),

$$\begin{aligned} \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\| = \|f'\| &\leq \mathbf{C}\|f' - S_k(f') + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\| \\ &= \mathbf{C}\|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A} - S_k(f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}) + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\| \\ &= \mathbf{C}\|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients with $\Delta_{pl} \leq \mathbf{C}$. Assume now that \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients. Take B, f, k and ε as in (3.7), and define $A = \{1, \dots, k\}$ with $k < \min B$. Hence, using Proposition 2.1,

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\| = \|f - S_k(f) + S_k(f)\| &\leq \mathbf{A}_p \sup\{\|f - S_k(f) + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\| : \varepsilon \in \Psi_A\} \\ &\stackrel{(3.4)}{\leq} \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl} \|f - S_k(f) + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|. \end{aligned}$$

The proof of a) is done.

Prove now b). Assume that \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients. Take $f, A, \varepsilon \in \Psi_A$ as in (3.2). Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|^p &\leq \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|^p + \|f\|^p \\ &\stackrel{(3.4)}{\leq} \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|^p + \Delta_{pl}^p \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|^p \end{aligned}$$

$$= (1 + \Delta_{pl}^p) \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|^p.$$

Thus, \mathcal{B} is C_{ql} -quasi-greedy for largest coefficients with $C_{ql} \leq (1 + \Delta_{pl}^p)^{1/p}$. The fact that \mathcal{B} is super-conservative with $\Delta_s \leq \Delta_{pl}$ follows from the definition.

Assume now that \mathcal{B} is Δ_s -super-conservative and C_{ql} -quasi-greedy for largest coefficients. Take $f, A, B, \varepsilon, \varepsilon'$ as in (3.4).

$$\begin{aligned} \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|^p &\leq \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|^p + \|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\|^p + \|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|^p \\ &\stackrel{(3.5)}{\leq} \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|^p + (1 + \Delta_s^p) \|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|^p \\ &\stackrel{(3.2)}{\leq} \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|^p + (1 + \Delta_s^p) C_{ql}^p \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|^p \\ &= (1 + (1 + \Delta_s^p) C_{ql}^p) \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|^p \end{aligned}$$

Thus, \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients with $\Delta_{pl} \leq (1 + (1 + \Delta_s^p) C_{ql}^p)^{1/p}$ and the proof is over. \square

Question 3.11. Is it possible to characterize super-conservativeness using conservativeness? That is, is there any property \mathbf{X} such that if \mathcal{B} is conservative with the Property \mathbf{X} then \mathcal{B} is super-conservative? This question is still open in the case of Banach spaces.

4. CHARACTERIZATION OF PARTIALLY-GREEDINESS

The following characterization will be useful to talk in the following section about renormings. Also, this theorem is given using a similar property that can be found in [7] and [3].

Theorem 4.1. *Let \mathcal{B} a basis in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} . \mathcal{B} is partially-greedy if and only if there exists a positive constant \mathbf{D} such that*

$$\|f\| \leq \mathbf{D} \|f - S_k(f) + z\|, \quad (4.1)$$

for every $f, z \in \mathbb{X}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $|\text{supp}(z)| < \infty$, $k < \min \text{supp}(z)$, $k \leq |\text{supp}(z)|$, $\text{supp}(f) \cap \text{supp}(z) = \emptyset$ and $\max_{n \in \text{supp}(f)} |e_n^*(f)| \leq \min_{n \in \text{supp}(z)} |e_n^*(z)|$. Moreover, $\inf \mathbf{D} = C_{pg}$.

Proof. Assume (4.1). Let $f \in \mathbb{X}$, A a greedy set of f with cardinality $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and take $k \leq m$. Define the elements $f' := f - P_A(f)$ and $z = P_A(f) - S_k(P_A(f))$. Of course, z and f' verifies the conditions of (4.1). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \|f - P_A(f)\| = \|f'\| &\leq \mathbf{D} \|f' - S_k(f') + z\| \\ &= \mathbf{D} \|f - P_A(f) - S_k(f - P_A(f)) + P_A(f) - P_A(S_k(f))\| \\ &= \mathbf{D} \|f - P_A(f) - S_k(f) + S_k(P_A(f)) + P_A(f) - S_k(P_A(f))\| \\ &= \mathbf{D} \|f - S_k(f)\|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, since this estimate works for any greedy set A and any $k \leq |A|$, the basis is C_{pg} -partially-greedy with $C_{pg} \leq \mathbf{D}$.

Assume now that \mathcal{B} is C_{pg} -partially-greedy basis and show (4.1). Take f, z , and k as in (4.1). Considering the element $g := f + z$, $\text{supp}(z)$ is a greedy set of g with $m = |\text{supp}(z)|$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\| = \|g - z\| &\leq C_{pg} \inf_{j \leq m} \|g - S_j(f + z)\| \\ &\leq C_{pg} \|g - S_k(f + z)\| \\ &\leq C_{pg} \|f - S_k(f) + z\|, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality holds for any k as in (4.1). Hence, (4.1) is proved and the proof is over. \square

Theorem 4.2. *Let \mathcal{B} a basis in a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} . The following are equivalent:*

- i) \mathcal{B} is partially-greedy.
- ii) \mathcal{B} is quasi-greedy and partially-symmetric for largest coefficients.
- iii) \mathcal{B} is quasi-greedy and super-conservative.
- iv) \mathcal{B} is partially-symmetric for largest coefficients and the truncation operator is uniformly bounded.
- v) \mathcal{B} is quasi-greedy and conservative.

Moreover, $\Delta_{pl} \leq C_{pg}$ and, in the particular case when \mathbb{X} is a p -Banach space, we also have

$$C_{pg} \leq \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl} \Gamma_t, \quad C_{qg} \leq 2^{1/p} C_{pg}.$$

Proof. i) \Rightarrow ii). The argument to show that the basis is partially-symmetric for largest coefficients follows from [8, Proposition 1.13]. Indeed, take $|A| \leq |B| < \infty$, $f \in \mathbb{X}$ such that $|\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \leq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $A < \text{supp}(f) \cup B$, $B \cap \text{supp}(f) = \emptyset$, $\varepsilon \in \Psi_A$ and $\varepsilon' \in \Psi_B$. Define now the element

$$x := f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A} + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B} + \mathbf{1}_D,$$

where $D = [1, \dots, m] \setminus A$ with $m := \max A$. Then, since $m = |A \cup D| \leq |B \cup D|$ and $B \cup D$ is a greedy set for x ,

$$\begin{aligned} \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\| &= \|x - P_{B \cup D}(x)\| \leq C_{pg} \inf_{k \leq |B \cup D|} \|x - S_k(x)\| \\ &\leq C_{pg} \|x - S_m(x)\| = C_{pg} \|f + \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients with $\Delta_{pl} \leq C_{pg}$. To show that \mathcal{B} is quasi-greedy, taking $k = 0$ in the definition of partially-greediness, we obtain that

$$\|f - P_A(f)\| \leq C_{pg} \|f\|,$$

for any finite greedy set A of f . Hence, \mathcal{B} is quasi-greedy with $C_{qg} \leq 2^{1/p} C_{pg}$.

ii) \Rightarrow iii), follows from the item b) of Proposition 3.10.

iii) \Rightarrow iv), follows from Theorem 3.6 and the item b) of Proposition 3.10.

iv) \Rightarrow i). Assume that \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients and the truncation operator is uniformly bounded with constant Γ_t . Take $f \in \mathbb{X}$, $P_B(f)$ with B a greedy set of f of cardinality m and $A = \{1, \dots, k\}$ with $k \leq m$. Then,

$$f - P_B(f) = P_{(A \cup B)^c}(f - S_k(f)) + P_{A \setminus B}(f).$$

Thus, taking $t := \min_{n \in B} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)|$, applying Proposition 2.1,

$$\|f - P_B(f)\| \leq \mathbf{A}_p \sup_{\eta \in \Psi_{A \setminus B}} \|P_{(A \cup B)^c}(f - S_k(f)) + t \mathbf{1}_{\eta(A \setminus B)}\| \quad (4.2)$$

If we select $\varepsilon \equiv \{\text{sign}(\mathbf{e}_n^*(f))\}$, applying the fact that \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetry for largest coefficients in combination with (4.2),

$$\begin{aligned} \|f - P_B(f)\| &\stackrel{(3.4)+(4.2)}{\leq} \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl} \|P_{(A \cup B)^c}(f - S_k(f)) + t \mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon(B \setminus A)}\| \\ &= \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl} \|\mathcal{T}(f - S_k(f), B \setminus A)\| \\ &\leq \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl} \Gamma_t \|f - S_k(f)\|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, since the last estimate works for any $k \leq |B|$ and any finite greedy set B , \mathcal{B} is C_{pg} -partially-greedy with $C_{pg} \leq \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl} \Gamma_t$.

iii) \Rightarrow v). This implication is trivial by definitions.

v) \Rightarrow iii). We only have to prove that \mathcal{B} is super-conservative. For that, consider $|A| \leq |B|$, $A < B$, $\varepsilon \in \Psi_A$ and $\varepsilon' \in \Psi_B$.

$$\|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon A}\| \stackrel{\text{Proposition 2.1}}{\leq} \mathbf{B}_p \sup_{D \subseteq A} \|\mathbf{1}_D\| \leq \mathbf{B}_p \Delta \|\mathbf{1}_B\|. \quad (4.3)$$

Now, applying [3, Lemma 2.2 (ii)], we obtain that

$$\|\mathbf{1}_B\| \leq \mathbf{B}_p C_{qg} \|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon' B}\|. \quad (4.4)$$

Thus, by (4.3) and (4.4), the proof is done. \square

The above theorem gives estimates for the partially-greedy constant using the partially-symmetry for largest coefficients constant and the truncation operator constant. We complete that result providing estimates of C_{pg} in terms of the quasi-greedy constant of the basis and some constants related to conservative-like properties.

Theorem 4.3. *Let \mathcal{B} be a basis of a p -Banach space \mathbb{X} . Assume that \mathcal{B} is C_{qg} -quasi-greedy. Then,*

i) *If \mathcal{B} is Δ -conservative, then \mathcal{B} is C_{pg} -partially-greedy with*

$$C_{pg} \leq C_{qg} (2 + (\mathbf{A}_p \mathbf{B}_p \Delta C_{qg}^2 \eta_p(C_{qg}))^p)^{1/p}.$$

ii) *If \mathcal{B} is Δ_s -super-conservative, then \mathcal{B} is C_{pg} -partially-greedy with*

$$C_{pg} \leq C_{qg} (2 + (\mathbf{A}_p \Delta_s \eta_p(C_{qg}))^p)^{1/p}.$$

iii) *If \mathcal{B} is Δ_{pl} -partially-symmetric for largest coefficients, then \mathcal{B} is C_{pg} -partially-greedy with*

$$C_{pg} \leq \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_{pl} C_{qg} (1 + C_{pg}^p \eta_p^p(C_{qg}))^{1/p}.$$

Proof. As in Theorem 4.2, take $f \in \mathbb{X}$, $P_B(f)$ with B a finite greedy set of cardinality m and $A = \{1, \dots, k\}$ with $k \leq m$. Then,

$$f - P_B(f) = P_{(A \cup B)^c}(f - S_k(f)) + P_{A \setminus B}(f).$$

Of course, since $B \setminus A$ is a greedy set of $f - S_k(f)$, under the hypothesis of quasi-greediness, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_{(A \cup B)^c}(f - S_k(f))\|^p &= \|f - S_k(f) - P_{B \setminus A}(f - S_k(f))\|^p \\ &\leq \|f - S_k(f)\|^p + \|P_{B \setminus A}(f - S_k(f))\|^p \\ &\leq 2C_{qg}^p \|f - S_k(f)\|^p. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|P_{(A \cup B)^c}(f - S_k(f))\| \leq 2^{1/p} C_{qg} \|f - S_k(f)\|. \quad (4.5)$$

i) By (4.5), we only need to control $\|P_{A \setminus B}(f)\|$.

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_{A \setminus B}(f)\| &\stackrel{\text{Proposition 2.1}}{\leq} \mathbf{B}_p \Delta \max_{n \in A \setminus B} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \|\mathbf{1}_{B \setminus A}\| \\ &\leq \mathbf{B}_p \Delta \min_{n \in B \setminus A} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \|\mathbf{1}_{B \setminus A}\| \\ &\leq \mathbf{A}_p \mathbf{B}_p \Delta C_{qg}^2 \eta_p(C_{qg}) \|P_{B \setminus A}(f)\|, \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

where the last inequality is due to [3, Theorem 3.10]. Now, taking into account that $B \setminus A$ is a greedy set for $f - S_k(f)$, since

$$\|P_{B \setminus A}(f)\| = \|P_{B \setminus A}(f - S_k(f))\| \leq C_{qg}\|f - S_k(f)\|,$$

by (4.5) and (4.6), we obtain the result.

ii) Taking $\varepsilon = \{\text{sign}(\mathbf{e}_n^*(f))\}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_{A \setminus B}(f)\| &\stackrel{\text{Proposition 2.1}}{\leq} \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_s \max_{n \in A \setminus B} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon(B \setminus A)}\| \\ &\leq \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_s \min_{n \in B \setminus A} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \|\mathbf{1}_{\varepsilon(B \setminus A)}\| \\ &\stackrel{\text{Theorem 3.6}}{\leq} \mathbf{A}_p \Delta_s C_{qg} \eta_p(C_{qg}) \|f - S_k(f)\|. \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

By (4.5) and (4.7), we obtain the estimate.

iii) Follows from iv) of Theorem 4.2 and Theorem 3.6.

The proof is done. \square

5. RENORMINGS OF PARTIALLY-GREEDY BASES

In [12], the authors continue with one of the most difficult problems in greedy approximation theory: renorming Banach spaces with greedy bases. In this paper, the authors characterized 1-greedy bases (generalizing the result proved in [5]) and, also, proved that, for a fixed $\varepsilon > 0$, it is possible to find a renorming in L_p , $1 < p < \infty$, such that the Haar system is $(1 + \varepsilon)$ -greedy, but it is unsolved if it is possible or not to get the constant 1. The topic of renorming Banach spaces with greedy bases continue nowadays and one recent paper talking about this theory is [4]. One of the most important keys in all of these papers is the use of convexity! Also, in Banach spaces, it is well known that a renorming $\|\cdot\|_0$ of $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$ has the form

$$\|f\|_0 = \max\{a\|f\|, \|T(f)\|_{\mathbb{Y}}\},$$

for some $0 < a < \infty$ and some bounded linear operator T from \mathbb{X} into a Banach space \mathbb{Y} .

Renorming quasi-Banach spaces with greedy bases has been recently studied in [3], where one of the most important tools is the following lemma:

Lemma 5.1 ([3, Lemma 11.1]). *Let $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$ be a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} . Assume that $\|\cdot\|_0 : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is such that, for every $t \in \mathbb{F}$ and for every $f \in \mathbb{X}$,*

- (1) $\|t f\|_0 = |t| \|f\|_0$,
- (2) $\|f\|_0 \approx \|f\|$.

Then, $\|\cdot\|_0$ is a renorming of $\|\cdot\|$.

This lemma allows us to have renormings of quasi-Banach spaces based on non-linear operators! Here, we follow the ideas of [3, Theorem 11.3] to give a renorming such that $C_{pg} = 1$.

Theorem 5.2. *Let \mathcal{B} a partially-greedy basis of a quasi-Banach space \mathbb{X} . Then, there is a renorming of \mathbb{X} with respect to which $C_{pg} = 1$.*

Proof. Based on Theorem 4.1, we introduce the following quantity:

$$\|f\|_a = \inf\{\|f - S_k(f) + z\| : (k, z) \in \mathcal{D}(f)\},$$

where $(k, z) \in \mathcal{D}(f)$ if $|\text{supp}(z)| < \infty$, $k < \min \text{supp}(z)$, $\text{supp}(z) \cap \text{supp}(f) = \emptyset$, $k \leq |\text{supp}(z)|$ and $\max_{n \in \text{supp}(f)} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(f)| \leq \min_{n \in \text{supp}(z)} |\mathbf{e}_n^*(z)|$. By Theorem 4.1, $\|f\|_a \approx \|f\|$ for $f \in \mathbb{X}$, so applying Lemma 5.1, $\|\cdot\|_a$ is a renorming of $\|\cdot\|$.

Take now $(k, z) \in \mathcal{D}(f)$ and write $g := f - S_k(f) + z$ and $A = \{1, \dots, k\}$. Take now $(m, y) \in \mathcal{D}(g)$ and define $B = \{1, \dots, m\}$, $B_1 = B \cap (\text{supp}(f - S_k(f)))$ and $B_2 = B \cap \text{supp}(z)$. Then,

$$g - S_m(g) = f - P_{A \cup B_1}(f) + z - P_{B_2}(z).$$

It is clear that $\text{supp}(z - P_{B_2}(z)) \cap \text{supp}(y) = \emptyset$ and

$$\begin{aligned} p = |A \cup B_1| &= k + m - |B_2| \\ &\leq |\text{supp}(z)| + |\text{supp}(y)| - |B_2| \\ &= |\text{supp}(z - P_{B_2}(z))| + |\text{supp}(y)| \\ &= |\text{supp}(z - P_{B_2}(z) + y)|. \end{aligned}$$

We infer that $(p, z - P_{B_2}(z) + y) \in \mathcal{D}(f)$ and

$$\|f\|_a \leq \|f - S_p(f) + z - P_{B_2}(z) + y\| = \|g - S_m(g) + y\|.$$

Taking the infimum over (m, y) we get $\|f\|_a \leq \|g\|_a$ and, based on the estimates of Theorem 4.1, the proof is done. \square

Final comments and open problems:

One of the main results in this paper is the characterization of partially-greediness in the world of quasi-Banach spaces under quasi-greediness and conservativeness (and another closed properties). This result is a generalization of the characterization of partially-greedy bases presented in [11] and [8] for Banach spaces. The main techniques to show our result are given in the recent paper [3]. One remark here is that, in [11], the authors introduced partially-greediness as in Remark 3.4 and characterize these bases under the condition of Schauder bases. In [8], the authors introduced, for Banach spaces, the definition of partially-greediness that we have used here and gave the characterization using Markushevich bases noting that, under the condition of Schauder, both definitions are equivalent.

Under this comment, the main question is the following: if \mathcal{B} is a semi-normalized Markushevich basis in a quasi-Banach (or Banach) space, are both definition equivalent? In the case of Banach spaces, one step in this direction is given in [8], but we don't have a general answer for this question.

Finally, note that the result concerning renormings is the continuation of some results presented in [3] and, for Banach spaces, it is unknown if it is possible or not to have a similar result.

ANNEX: SUMMARY OF THE MOST IMPORTANT CONSTANTS

Symbol	Name of constant	Ref. equation
Δ_{pl}	Partially-symmetry for largest coeffs. constant	(3.4)
Δ_s	Super-conservativeness constant	(3.5)
Δ	Conservativeness constant	(3.5)
C_{qg}	Quasi-greedy constant	(3.1)
C_{ql}	Quasi-greedy for largest coeffs. constant	(3.2)
C_{pg}	Partially-greedy constant	(3.3)
Γ_u	Restricted truncation operator constant	Section 3.2
Γ_t	Truncation operator constant	Section 3.2

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